

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.1.3: Creation of anthropogenic corridors

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Project leader and contributors:

- Asuka Koyama (asukoyama@affrc.go.jp)

Data curator(s):

- Asuka Koyama (asukoyama@affrc.go.jp)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.3.1.3 assesses the role of creation of anthropogenic corridors as drivers of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: corridor AND (pathway OR road OR railway OR canal OR tunnel OR pipeline) AND (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) AND (review OR “systematic review” OR “meta-analysis” OR “meta analysis” OR “literature review” OR “synthesis” OR “synthesis matrix”)

Search 2: corridor AND (pathway OR road OR railway OR canal OR tunnel OR pipeline) AND (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) AND (review OR “meta analysis” OR synthesis)

Search 3: (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) with some specific keywords (e.g., highway, railway)

- Search engine:

Search 1: Web of knowledge

Search 2 and 3: Google scholar

- Date:

Search 1: 14 September 2019

Search 2 and 3: 24 September 2019

- Searched time period:

Search 2: 2000-2019

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria:

Number of search result:

Search 1:22

Search 2:8

Search 3:6

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type (review) excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2: Searched with above terms with timespan of 2000 to 2019, then excluded low relevant papers from Top 50 papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 3: Searched with above terms with timespan of 2000 to 2019, then excluded low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 10

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: 46 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]

-Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)